

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF FOLDABLE SHELL EXTENDIBLE TUBE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

FSET (Foldable Shell Extendible Tube) is a new concept of deployable structures for space applications. This structure has advantages over an inflatable tube in that it doesn't need any gas and there is little possibility of unexpected behavior during developing. In this study, extending behavior and deployment force of the FSET are discussed by comparing the results of FEM and experiments. Finite element models of the FSET were analyzed for different materials and film's clearance, and the experiments were conducted to verify the validity of the analyses. FEM and experimental results show that the FSET with larger film's clearance is more likely to extend, and that its deployment force decreases. Furthermore, FEM results suggest that the deployment force becomes zero or close to zero during extending regardless of materials of a component.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Inflatable booms are promising candidates for a range of space applications because they have advantages of high packaging efficiency, low system complexity and a simple deployment mechanism [1]. They are made of membrane or film and can hold their shapes after gas is injected. However, they also have disadvantages of unpredictable deployment sequence and a gas container taking up space.

To solve these problems, a new concept of deployable structures has been introduced [2]. The structure is called as Foldable Shell Extendible Tube (FSET) and an example of the FSET is shown in Fig. 1. It constitutes of a foldable film cylinder and pieces of flexible shells. The film cylinder has a folding pattern allowing the structure to change from a cylindrical to flat shape [3]. The separate shells are placed on the film leaving creases of the film free to be foldable. Because this structure is stable in an extended shape, i.e. a cylinder, its folded shape autonomously changes to the extended shape shown in Fig. 2 and releases strain energy of the film and the shells. This structure is promising for use in space as a new deployable structure, but its developing behavior has not yet been known.

In this paper, behavior of the FSET shown in Fig. 2 was studied for different materials and different clearance between the shells (width of the creasing portion of film). Using Finite Element Method (FEM)

software, differences in deployment force and strain energy of each extending shape of those FSETs were investigated in order to measure the deployability of them. Analyses were carried out assuming that the material of the shell was elastically isotropic or orthotropic, and the film was elastically isotropic. Basic behaviour of the FSET was investigated by using isotropic shells, and then analyses of the FSET with orthotropic shells were conducted considering application of carbon fiber reinforced plastics to the FSET. Experiments were also carried out to check the validity of the analyses for isotropic shells.

Figure 1: Concept of the FSET [2].

Figure 2: Behavior of the FSET.

1.2 Folding Pattern of FSET

Folding pattern of the FSET analyzed in this paper is shown in Fig. 3. This is a development view of a unit of the whole FSET. This unit is made of six regular hexagons. This figure shows that dotted lines are valley folds and solid lines are mountain folds. There are other patterns that can be folded from cylindrical to flat, but the folding pattern shown in Fig. 3 is only considered in this study.

Figure 3: A unit of the FSET analyzed in this paper.

2 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 Modeling

Models of the FSET shown in Fig. 4 were analyzed by the FEM software, Marc 2013. The FSET was made of the film and shell, and rigid plates were placed on the top and bottom of the FSET. The thickness of the rigid plates was 3 mm. Four-node shell elements were used in this model. Tables 1-4 show geometric and material properties of the shell and film. The material of the shell was isotropic material (Case A) or T300/LTM45-EL UD composite [4] (Case B). The fiber direction of the UD composite applied to the shell was along z-axis direction (Case B-1) and cylindrical circumferential direction (Case B-2) shown in Fig. 5. Analyses were carried out on the conditions of the film's clearance $c = 0.9, 1.2, 1.5$ and 1.8 mm in the case A, $c = 1.2$ and 1.5 mm in the case B-1, and $c = 0.9$ and 1.2 mm in the case B-2. The film's clearance c is defined in Fig. 4.

Six nodes of the film corresponding to the point A of each regular hexagon were fixed except z-axis direction and cylindrical center direction (Fig. 6). Here, the point A is the center of a regular hexagon. Three nodes of the film corresponding to the point B and points placed 120 and 240 degrees distant from the point B around the z-axis were fixed in z-axis direction in order to avoid rigid body displacement.

Figure 4: Finite element model of the FSET.

Figure 5: Definition of fiber directions.

Figure 6: Definition of points for boundary conditions and Unit 1.

Table 1: Geometric properties of the FSET.

Radius of FSET [mm]	25.0
Initial height of FSET H_e [mm]	105.8
Thickness of shell [mm]	0.72
Thickness of film [mm]	0.16

Table 2: Material properties of the film.

Young Modulus E [GPa]	Poisson Ratio ν
3.40	0.30

Table 3: Material properties of the shell in the case of isotropic material.

Young Modulus E [GPa]	Poisson Ratio ν
2.40	0.30

Table 4: Material properties of the shell in the case of unidirectional composite.
(T300/LTM45-EL UD composite [4])

E_{11} [GPa]	$E_{22} = E_{33}$ [GPa]	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	ν_{23}	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ [GPa]	G_{23} [GPa]
127	9.1	0.31	0.45	5.6	4.0

2.2 Analytical Procedures

In order to investigate the deployment force and strain energy of the FSET during extending phase, analyses were carried out in the following sequence.

1. Nodal loads were applied to the 18 nodes of the film in the inward radial direction of the cylinder of the extended shape. 18 nodes correspond to the points C of each regular hexagon. The upper and lower rigid plates were moved in the squeezing direction of the FSET.
2. The radial nodal loads were removed so that only the force by the plates was applied to the FSET.
3. The plates were moved in the direction to fold and extend the FSET.
4. The deployment force of the FSET was calculated as the release rate of the strain energy of the shell. The reason why the deployment force was not defined as the reaction force of the rigid plates was to avoid the influence of the film on the deployment force. Here, when the strain energy of the shell increased during extending, i.e. the energy release rate was negative, the deployment force was regarded as zero.

Analyses were carried out under the conditions of nonlinear static, small strain, and large rotation.

3 EXPERIMENT

Experiments were conducted in order to check the validity of the finite element analyses of isotropic materials. Deployment forces of two FSETs with film's clearance $c = 0.9$ and 1.5 mm were measured. The material of the shell was polycarbonate and its material properties were the same as those of the analytical model shown in Table 3. Composition of the FSETs was polyimide film, thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) film, shell, and TPU film from the inside to the outside of the FSETs. TPU was used to bond the polyimide film and the shell. Dimensions of the FSETs were the same as Table 1.

The testing machine was AGS-1kNX (Fig. 7). A Teflon sheet was pasted on the surfaces of both jigs to reduce friction between the FSET and the jigs. The distance between the upper and lower jigs was 110 mm at the start of the test, and the test speed was 50 mm/min. In the test, the upper jig was lowered until the distance between the jigs became 50 mm, and then the folded FSET was inserted between the jigs. The upper jig was lowered until the distance between the jigs was 20 mm and then was raised in order to measure the deployment force of the FSET during folding and extending.

Figure 7: AGX-1kNX.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of finite element analyses and experiments are discussed in this chapter. In the first section, the FSET with isotropic shell (Case A) is considered. Strain energy and deployment force at a specific height of the FSET are shown and discussed with experimental results. In the next section, the FSET with orthotropic shell (Case B) is considered. Differences in deployment force between each orientation are discussed.

4.1 Isotropic

In order to avoid self-contact penetration of the FSET, analyses of Case A were performed in the range of $0.25 < H/H_e$. Plates were moved from $H/H_e = 0.87$ to 0.25 in the squeezing direction of the FSET, and then moved from $H/H_e = 0.25$ to 1.0 to extend it.

Figure 8 shows the shapes of the FSET at $H/H_e = 0.55$ in the finite element analysis and experiment. From this figure, it is observed that the unit 1-1 of the shell in the finite element analysis result is less folded than that in the experimental result. It is considered due to the contact between the films in the circles shown in Fig. 8a. In these areas, many films interfere with each other when the FSET is folded, so the films corresponding to the line between the circles in Fig. 8a are hard to be folded, and as a result, the unit 1-1 of the shell in Fig. 8a is less folded compared to that in Fig. 8b at the same height.

Figure 9 shows the relationship between strain energy of the FSET with various film's clearances and each extending height H in finite element analyses. Note that H is normalized by the initial height H_e . Considering Figs. 9a and 9b, it is confirmed that the effect of the film on the strain energy of the FSET is large. However, this effect is overestimated because of the element types applied to the film and film's material properties. The four-node shell elements were applied to the film, and the Young modulus of the film was set to the constant value and no yield point was assumed. In the analysis, therefore, the strain energy of the folded film was exceedingly large. That's why the deployment force was calculated as not the reaction force of the rigid plates but the release rate of the strain energy only of the shell.

Figure 10 shows the analytical and experimental results of the deployment force at each height of the FSET with different clearances. In the analyses, the FSET with $c = 0.9$ mm became stable and stopped extending at $H/H_e = 0.95$, and the FSET with $c = 1.5$ mm continued to extend after $H/H_e = 0.95$. Here, the calculation in the case of $c = 1.5$ mm did not converge prior to the full extension of the FSET. In the experiments, the FSET with $c = 0.9$ mm became stable and its deployment force was zero at $H/H_e = 0.48$, so it was manually extended at $H/H_e = 0.70$ where the value of its deployment force was positive again. The deployment force of the FSET with $c = 1.5$ mm was always greater than zero. These results suggest that the FSET with larger film's clearance is easier to extend.

As shown in Fig. 10, the deployment forces of the FSET in the analyses and experiments have a similar tendency. Thus, it is considered that the method to calculate the deployment force of the FSET from the release rate of the strain energy of the shell is effective to some extent.

In the experiments, the deployment forces during extending were lower than those during folding at the same height. It is assumed that loss of energy because of friction between the shells affected this difference.

Figure 10 also shows that the deployment force becomes larger at high and low value of H/H_e when the clearance c becomes smaller. However, the deployment force is close to zero in both the experiments and analyses in the range of $0.40 \leq c \leq 0.60$, so it is necessary to increase the deployment force in this range for practical use of the FSET.

Figure 8: Shape of the FSET at $H/H_e = 0.55$.
Contour plot means z displacement. (a) Finite element analysis (b) Experiment

Figure 9: Relationship between strain energy and normalized height in finite element analyses.
 (a) FSET (b) Shells of FSET (c) Shell of Unit 1-1 (d) Shell of Unit 1-2
 (Unit 1-1 and 1-2 are predefined in Fig. 6)

Figure 10: Relationship between deployment force of the FSET and normalized height.

4.2 Orthotropic

In this section, differences in the results of Case B-1 (z-axis direction) and Case B-2 (cylindrical circumferential direction) are discussed. Because of a problem of convergence caused by self-contraction of the FSET, analyses were carried out for $H/H_e > 0.40$ in Case B-1 and for $H/H_e > 0.51$ in Case B-2.

Figures 11 and 12 show the relationship between the deployment force of the FSET and each extending height H for Case B-1 and Case B-2 in the analyses, respectively. H is normalized by the initial height H_e .

In Case B-1 (Fig. 11), the FSET whose fiber orientation is along z-axis direction, there was a stable point in the case of $c = 1.2$ mm at $H/H_e = 0.45$ unlike $c = 1.5$ mm. Here, the analysis in the case of $c = 1.5$ mm did not converge at about $H/H_e = 0.95$. Figure 11 shows that the deployment force is zero in the range of $0.40 < H/H_e < 0.75$ in the case of $c = 1.2$ and 1.5 mm, respectively. It is also confirmed that the deployment force of the FSET with $c = 1.5$ mm increases in the range of $0.75 \leq H/H_e$. However, the analysis in this range was unstable because the FSET drastically returned to the cylindrical shape, so this value can be overestimated.

In case B-2 (Fig. 12), the FSET whose fiber orientation is along cylindrical circumferential direction, on the other hand, there was no stable point in all the case. Here, the analyses in the case of $c = 0.9$ and 1.2 mm did not converge at about $H/H_e = 0.85$. From Fig. 12, it is confirmed that the deployment force is always greater than zero in the range of $0.51 < H/H_e < 0.67$, and that the deployment force becomes smaller as the film clearance c is increased. However, Fig. 12 also shows that the deployment force is zero in the range of $0.72 < H/H_e$ in the both cases of film's clearance. Therefore, it is necessary to find a stacking sequence which makes deployment force always greater than zero. Further experiments are also required to verify the validity of the analyses of Case B.

Figure 11: Relationship between deployment force of the FSET whose fiber orientation is along z-axis direction (Case B-1) and normalized height.

Figure 12: Relationship between deployment force of the FSET whose fiber orientation is along cylindrical circumferential direction (Case B-2) and normalized height.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, in order to investigate extending behavior and deployment force of the FSET, finite element analyses were carried out on the conditions of various values of the film's clearance c and two

materials of the shell, and then experiments were conducted to check the validity of the analyses. The results obtained can be summarized as follows.

1. The method of calculating the deployment force of the FSET from the release rate of the strain energy of the shell is effective to some extent.
2. FSET is easier to extend as the film's clearance c is larger.
3. The deployment force increases at a certain range of height as the film's clearance c is smaller.
4. The deployment force becomes zero or close to zero during extending in both case A and case B.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Schenk, A. D. Viquerat, K. A. Seffen, and S. D. Guest. "Review of inflatable booms for deployable space structures: packing and rigidization." *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets* 51.3 (2014): 762-778.
- [2] A. Watanabe, T. Hori, and H. Ito. "Development of the Foldable shell Extendible Tubes." *Proceedings of the Space Sciences and Technology Conference*, Kurume, Japan, Vol. 62, JSASS-2018-4300, 2018.
- [3] T. Nojima. "Modelling of folding patterns in flat membranes and cylinders by origami." *JSME International Journal Series C Mechanical Systems, Machine Elements and Manufacturing* 45.1 (2002): 364-370.
- [4] V. A. Phadnis, F. Makhadmeh, A. Roy, and V.V. Silberschmidt. "Drilling in carbon/epoxy composites: experimental investigations and finite element implementation." *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 47, pp 41-51, 2013.